

“IMAGE” ESSENCE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND IT’S ROLE IN
PROMOTION IN A COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: In this research paper investigated essence of the concept of image in various aspects, revealing the main approaches to its understanding. They reveal the criteria and components of its readiness to form an image, which indirectly affects the successful implementation of educational goals in modern conditions and the construction of the entire educational process.

Keywords: image, formation, readiness, skills, educational institution, leadership qualities, effect.

1.Introduction

The problem of image is one of the priorities in social and humanitarian knowledge, as evidenced by the emergence of pedagogical imageology as a modern innovative educational technology. The analysis of the concept of image and its social nature is becoming interdisciplinary: image appears in various guises - as a social sign (or symbol) that must be followed; as a form of self-expression; as a factor in socialization and integration into society; as a condition for success, etc. Image has the property of creating attitudes and impressions regarding certain phenomena occurring in social institutions and in the social environment. In addition, image creates a system of values - ideological and moral, corresponding to the real (or imaginary) social context, it influences the nature of social interactions and communications. In the broadest sense, image contributes to the formation of a certain picture of the world. Such “abilities” of the image arise from its broad applicability: it is “a category that is universally applicable to any object that becomes the subject of social cognition: to a person (personal image), an organization (corporate image), a social position (the image of a politician), a profession (the image of a lawyer, etc.), an education (the image of a graduate of a university, college, lyceum, etc.), a trademark, objects, individual consumer characteristics of material objects (quality image), etc.” [17].

2.Analysis and results

The problem of forming a positive image of a leader is one of the key problems of modernization of education in modern conditions, very important and relevant. Formation of the image of a leader is a process during which a certain planned image is created based on available resources. The purpose of creating an image is to increase competitiveness, attract investments, establish and expand partnerships.

Thus, despite the rapid development of the education system, many contradictions arise, determining the relevance of the problem under study and awareness of the need to form a positive image of the heads of educational institutions.

The purpose of the article is to substantiate the need for targeted formation of a positive image of the head of an educational organization in modern conditions.

To achieve this goal, the article sets and solves the following tasks:

1) to analyze the psychological and pedagogical literature on the problem of defining the essence of the concept of the image of a leader;

2) to consider approaches to its definition, including components, image criteria, as well as factors of effective formation of a positive image of the head of an educational organization in modern conditions.

The state of scientific development of the research problem. The formation of image in their works was considered by many specialists, both in the field of management and marketing, advertising, etc. A significant contribution to the development of this problem was made by V.M. Shepel, L.A. Lobareva, G.I. Marchenko, I.A. Noskov, R.F. Romashkina, A. Pelikh, T. Kizilova, A. Pronchenko, P. Gurevich, L. Benediktova, G.G. Pocheptsov and others.

The problem of forming a positive image of a leader was studied by N.V. Krotova, E.V. Klepper, A. Eropkin and others.

The development of modern imageology was of interest to such researchers as N.V. Galiullina, N.I. Levshina, A.Yu. Panasyuk, G.G. Pocheptsov, V.M. Shepel. The essence of the formation of the image of the leader, its nature, structure and factors are described in publications in the following areas: management and marketing (for example, A. Anderson, P. Drucker, M. Mescon, M. Albert, F. Khedouri, A.A. Altshuller), sociology and political science (A.E. Binetsky, A.D. Karnyshev), psychology (E.B. Perelygina, V.A. Petrovsky), pedagogy (D.A. Belukhin).

Psychological aspects of the formation of the image of a professional leader were covered in their scientific works by E.V. Grishunina, P.S. Gurevich, R.F. Romashkina, V.M. Shepel and others.

At the moment, the process of image formation is relevant for all organizations, institutions, political and public figures, etc., who strive to gain a certain position in society, master new spheres of influence, etc. [9, 10]. The idea of image as a certain value has been established in the public consciousness, the presence and quality of which determines success in life, as well as the success of any activity, be it collective or individual activity.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem, to which the designated article is devoted. Despite the presence of many works in the designated area, it is worth considering the essence of the concept of the image of the leader, defining the criteria, considering the approaches and components of forming a positive image of the leader. After all, it is the personality of the leader and his main strengths that play a decisive role in the activities of any enterprise, especially in the field of educational services. It is the leader who contributes to strengthening the competitiveness of the educational institution, to attract talented youth and qualified personnel in order to preserve and strengthen the potential of the educational institution. Effective management of the organization entirely depends on the formed positive image of the leader, since the leader is its first person.

V. M. Shepel understands image as appearance, i.e. the form of a person's life manifestation, thanks to which attractive personal, business and professional characteristics are put on display for "public viewing" [14, 15].

A. V. Petrovsky M. G. Yaroshevsky Define image as a stereotyped image of a specific object that exists in the mass consciousness, and this concept refers to a specific person, but can also apply to a specific product, profession, organization [11].

I. A. Fedorov a system of social programming of the spiritual life and behavior of subjects (which can be both individuals and groups) by general civilizational and mental stereotypes and symbols of group behavior, mediated by the power of motivation for success, the standard of the desired impression [13].

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G. M. Andreeva is a specific "image" of the perceived object, in which the angle of perception is purposefully shifted and only certain aspects of the object or phenomenon are emphasized [2]. I. Hoffman represents the art of impression management [12].

I. D. Ladanov Considers it as an image of an authoritative person with a high social status, traces a close relationship between image and authority and status of a person [8].

A. Yu. Panasyuk as an opinion formed about someone by a certain group of people and forming the basis of a businessman's reputation [7].

A. S. Pelikh T. G. Kizilova A. G. Pronchenko assessment of a person by people around him, self-presentation, construction of a person's own image for others, ability to behave with people in business and informal settings [10].

L. A. Zolotovskaya as an artificial image that is formed in the public or individual consciousness by mass media [5].

V. P. Delia, is created by advertising with the aim of forming a certain attitude towards an object in the mass consciousness, taking into account both the real properties of objects and the non-existent ones attributed [4].

D. V. Zhuravlev defines it as a holistic vision of a specific social object, which is built on the basis of its stereotypical perception, an emotionally charged schematized image of this object, presented in the consciousness of its social environment, most often used in relation to a specific person, but can also be applied to a group of people, an organization, a product, a profession [5].

N. V. Galiullina, N. I. Levshina associated with his character traits, the quality of his activities and the peculiarities of interaction with the teaching staff and other subjects of the educational process [3].

Thus, image is a multifaceted phenomenon. On the one hand, it can be considered as an emotionally charged image of someone or something, an idea or opinion formed by a certain group of people regarding an object, on the other hand - as a means of development and self-improvement of the individual. We believe that the basis of the image of a leader is the essential characteristics of him as a person - moral and ethical qualities, professionalism and business qualities, external data (personal attractiveness, culture of behavior) - all this and much more allow us to judge the activities of the organization as a whole. Summarizing the above definitions of the concept of "image", it can be said that in modern science (management, marketing, psychology, sociology, etc.) two main approaches to its understanding have developed: 1) the first approach unites authors (G.M. Andreeva, I.D. Ladanov, V.M. Shepel, M.G. Yaroshevsky), who consider image as an image of someone or something formed in the mind, emotionally colored and with inherent characteristics, close to a stereotype;

2) the second approach is based on the point of view of such authors as O.S. Vikhansky, A.B. Zverintsev, Yu.A. Panasyuk, who define image as a representation or opinion formed by a certain group of people regarding some object.

In this regard, we have identified the criteria for the image of the head of an educational organization, which are the criteria for its formation. Such as:

1) personal characteristics: appearance, character traits, temperament, voice and speech, sociability, spirituality and morality, psycho-emotional state, etc. Acquired life qualities, such as resilience in difficult life situations, persistence in achieving results, the ability to self-develop, etc.;

2) social characteristics: orientation towards a certain target audience and compliance with its requirements, marital status, status and position among colleagues, subordinates, higher authorities, parents, etc.;

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- 3) the personal mission of the leader: awareness of the meaning of their own activities, achievement of their priority goals and objectives, the ability to convey their thoughts to the team, etc.;
- 4) the value orientations of the leader: social and moral values, interests, subjective social position, patriotism, etc.

It is worth noting that the formation of a positive image of the head of an educational organization is also influenced by objective and subjective factors [1].

We attribute the objective factors to society, including the factor of social expectations and assessments; political trends in the republic (state, world); historical experience in education; folk traditions, customs; the immediate environment, in particular the family; the teaching staff, the educational environment.

Subjective factors include: the factor of personal and professional development, professional mobility and competence, social stability. It is worth noting here that the management style also has a great influence on the formation of a positive image of both the leader and the overall image of the educational organization.

3. Conclusions

Conclusions on this study and prospects for further research in this direction. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, we have established that image is the most important component of management activity, and its possession is an essential professional characteristic of the head of an educational institution, directly related to his personal and professional-pedagogical qualities. A positive image of an educational institution is a conscious impression based on an assessment of the personal and professional qualities of the head of an educational organization that meet social criteria and norms, the demands of the education system and society that dominate at the current stage of its development. It is the head who implements the competitiveness of the educational institution in these difficult conditions of our time, expands cooperation, and establishes partnerships. Therefore, the appearance of the head not only has a leading influence on the formation

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of a positive image of the educational institution, but also affects the emotional and psychological climate in the teaching staff, the process of exchanging information between teaching staff, society, and students, which is necessary for quick and effective decision-making. However, we believe that it is necessary to solve the problem of forming a positive image of a modern head of an educational institution at the stage of training at a pedagogical university, since every teacher should be familiar with the basics of management.

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